

On the Corpuscular Nature of Light, Gamma Radiation, and "Electromagnetic Waves"

Abstract:

This paper challenges the traditional wave theory of light and Maxwell's equations in their modern interpretation. The author proposes a model where light and electromagnetic waves are not oscillations of an abstract field, but a sequence of closed ether vortices ("tori" or "doughnuts") with alternating rotation. This corpuscular approach explains polarization through the ellipticity of the vortices and defines the physical meaning of Planck's constant as rotational energy. The work calls for a return to classical physical intuition, rejecting mathematical abstractions like space-time curvature and Higgs bosons.

Keywords: light, gamma radiation, "electromagnetic waves"

It is sad and bitter to realize that over the past century, physics has turned into a cesspool of insane physical ideas, on which more than one generation of physicists has been raised. The tragedy of the consequences of this can hardly be underestimated, and it is very difficult to introduce alternative ideas into such an environment. Objectively speaking, modern physics is a religious teaching with a series of unshakable dogmas. Let us try to shake one of them.

The elucidation of the physical nature of light, gamma radiation, and EM waves cannot be considered complete today, despite the universal recognition of the wave nature of light and the triumphant recognition of Maxwell's equations. However, in the history of the development of ideas about the nature of light and EM waves, one very important detail is deliberately suppressed. Maxwell derived his equations based on the concept of the existence of the ether—a medium that permeates all bodies and fills all space, capable of being set in motion and transmitting motion to matter. Following Einstein, the medium was subsequently removed, declared a redundant appendage, leaving only the "naked" mathematics of equations, deprived of their original physical meaning and content.

Since the publication of the equations, much experimental material and ideas clarifying the concepts of the ether medium have appeared. Analysis of this material leads to the understanding that the model of the ether as an ideal fluid, as postulated by Maxwell, is a flawed hypothesis. The ether is a medium with completely specific properties and its own structure of organized movements. The ether medium is discrete; its elements are formed by the movement of a lower level of structural organization of matter. The absence of mass in ether particles physically means their original isolation from surrounding particles of their level.(1)

In a medium whose particles do not possess the property of mass, a wave process is impossible, because any manifestations of elastic properties or resistance to shear deformations are possible only in the presence of the inertial mass of its elements. Therefore, the concepts of light and EM waves as a wave process in the ether medium are erroneous. Analysis of radiation processes shows that "EM waves" are formed by a periodic current in a conductor, which forms two causally related ether toroids every half-period.(1) When the current becomes zero, the internal toroid disappears, and the external one is released and begins its self-motion in the ether. Light is formed when electrons detach from atoms, where the electrostatic field transforms into a periodic chain of interconnected toroids—Planck particles, each carrying the rotational energy equal to Planck's constant. Hard gamma radiation is formed according to a similar scenario during the decay or transformation of nucleons.

In this understanding, a photon is a chain of interconnected, self-moving ether toroids of various lengths. Newton was right in assuming that light is corpuscles. A corpuscle in this case is understood as a closed movement of the ether. According to this model, light and "EM waves" represent a periodic chain of closed, localized ether movements moving in the surrounding ether in the axial direction—a self-moving, periodic succession of "doughnuts." If these "doughnuts" are elliptical, the major axis coincides with the plane of polarization. This model confirms that there is no electrical component in the propagation of light, as the electric field exists only as long as it is associated with an elementary particle.

In conclusion, the neglect of philosophy by physicists is very costly to humanity, leading to the dead ends of illusory concepts like Higgs bosons, antimatter, and the Big Bang. Truly, "The Emperor has no clothes!"

References

1. Kuzmin I. N., "Are Newton's Laws Legitimate?" (Electronic resource), 2011. This work establishes the foundational model of the ether as a continuous medium and describes elementary particles as stable toroidal vortices. URL: kulichki.net

Note: This article was translated from Russian. The author does not speak English fluently and may not be able to respond to comments or participate in discussions in English.